

Perception of Female Undergraduates on Drug Abuse in Kano State, Nigeria: Implications for Counselling

Ahmad Salisu Abdullahi*

Department of Sociology, Federal University Dutse, Dutse, Nigeria

Hafsat Salisu Abdullahi

Department of Psychology and Education, Nigeria Police Academy, Wudil, Nigeria

Article Information

Suggested Citation:

Abdullahi, A.S. & Abdullahi, H.S. (2023). Perception of Female Undergraduates on Drug Abuse in Kano State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 1(2), 245-257.

DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2023.1\(2\).21](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2023.1(2).21)

* Corresponding author:

Ahmad Salisu Abdullahi

e-mail: ahmad.salisu@fud.edu.ng

Abstract:

The abuse of drugs by female undergraduate students is becoming alarming, posing serious repercussions for society in general. This study examined the perception of female undergraduates on drug abuse by female university students as perceived by female undergraduate students in Kano State. The study used a sample size of 306 female undergraduate students (selected using proportionate sampling technique) from Faculty of Education in BUK¹, KUST² and YUMSUK³. A validated instrument, DAI⁴ was used to collect relevant data. The reliability of DAI was established using the test-retest method. PPMC was used to compute the correlation coefficient of the instrument and reliability index of 0.79 was obtained. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research

questions, while t-test for independent sample and analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to test the three null hypotheses of the study. The findings of the study indicated that Benylin is the most commonly abused drug among female university students in Kano State, there is a difference in the perception of female undergraduates on drug abuse prevalence among female university students in Kano State based on university, in favour of BUK with the highest mean score of 8.04. Based on the findings, it is recommended among others that: the sales of benylin and other commonly abused drug within university campuses should be controlled by university authorities.

Keywords: *drug, drug abuse, female undergraduates.*

Introduction

Drug abuse can be traced to the emergence of modern pharmaceuticals, which paved the way for the availability of modern substances to awaken, sedate, and excite. Historically, people have used herbs, leaves, and plants to cure illness, gain extra energy, or relieve work stress. Drugs properly administered have been a societal blessing. What begins as a measure of relaxation often evolves in time into a problem of dependence and abuse (Muraguri, 2004).

Fundamentally, drugs are either substances that, when consumed in considerable quantity, intoxicate and affect someone's physical and mental balance, reasoning, sense of judgement, and behaviour; or substances that are used in the prevention or treatment of diseases, illnesses, ailments, and sicknesses.

Drug is any substance other than food that affects the structure and functioning of a living organism due to its chemical nature (Siro, 2014). It is mainly used to sedate, excite, arouse, induce

sleep, slim or cure (Abdullahi, 2003). The development of modern pharmaceuticals appears to be like a double-edged sword. While drugs rightly and legally administered make it easier and perhaps faster to cure illness, drugs wrongly and illegally administered negatively affect the wellbeing and normal functioning of an organism. Today, the abuse of drugs has become a universal phenomenon that cuts across social strata. Both developed and developing societies are facing an increasing challenge of drug abuse, especially because youth, who are supposedly, seen as leaders of tomorrow and agents of change, are at the vanguard of its perpetration. The usage and abuse of drugs is very common among adolescents, and it can result in serious repercussions (Nalini et al., 2016).

Garba (2003) defined drug abuse as the non-medical use of drugs that can alter mood and perception and have the ability to make the user continue to want to use the drug in spite of the health, social, and physical impairments the drug causes. Drug abuse can also be the improper use of drugs or alcohol to the degree that the consequences are defined as detrimental to the user or to society (Igbo, 2007). Haladu (2003) explained the term drug abuse as the excessive and persistent self-administration of a drug without regard to medically or culturally accepted patterns. For Priyanka & Ankita (2016), drug abuse is an illness that can be characterised as the destructive use of substances that causes many health-related and socio behavioural challenges. It is also the use of drugs when they are not medically necessary, when they are used against legal prohibition, or when there is excessive use of drugs without conformity to medical directives. Drug abuse can also be an illness when it becomes addictive.

Drug abuse has become a global phenomenon. Accordingly, the menace of drug abuse is not new to Nigerian society. Nigeria is witnessing an upsurge of drug-related problems as the country recently graduated or transitioned from the status of a drug-consuming nation to that of a drug-producing one. There has been widespread drug abuse among youths, as reported by most of the media in Nigeria. Similarly, reports from

the National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA) indicated that there is a high rate of youths abusing drugs across the country. Based on this report, there is every tendency that students in tertiary institutions as well as universities (the majority of whom are youths) are affected by the menace. Recently, the illegal use of drugs among university students has been recognised as a global public health challenge (Yi et al., 2017).

There is alarming evidence of the prevalence of drug abuse among students (Oliha, 2014). Social vices like drug abuse are very common on the campuses of Nigerian universities (Ibu & Eni, 2018). Okoro & Lahai (2021) revealed that a considerable proportion of undergraduates in Nigeria use drugs. Many undergraduate students in Nigeria are becoming drug dependent, which is a major consequence of drug abuse. Nigeria's educational institutions are dominated by drugs such as morphine, heroine, tobacco, cough syrup, tramadol, Valium 5, and Chinese capsules that youthful students commonly abuse (Ibrahim et al., 2019). Atwoli, Mungla, Ndungu, Kinoti & Ogot (2011) found a prevalence of substance use among college and university students in a low income country, with the most commonly used substances being alcohol and cigarettes.

The abuse of drugs and many, other socially problematic behaviours are seen as male-dominated behaviours. However, the rate at which female youths are engaging in drug abuse is becoming more alarming. Asagba, Agberotimi & Olaseni (2021) argued that there is evidence suggesting a rise in the level of female involvement in substance or drug use. The current trend of substance abuse among women is troubling and has become an issue of major national concern (Adenugba & Okeshola, 2018). Reports by the National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA) have revealed an increasing involvement of women in drug abuse. Among the increasing percentage of female youths engaging in drug abuse, a lot of these female youths are undergraduate students or have started abusing drugs as undergraduate students. The prevalence of drug abuse among female undergraduates is becoming a serious negative

development that is affecting their personal development. It is seriously becoming an issue to which everyone's attention is being drawn, as long as that person is conscious of what brought about improved societal welfare and peaceful coexistence among the teeming population. It is a behaviour disorder that is destroying the ethical standards of many societies.

The use of drugs among college and university students remains an important area of research due to the implications of early drug dependence on the future of youth (Atwoli et al., 2011). Accordingly, most of these young students are not fully aware of the magnitude of the problem or its long-term consequences, and even if they are, they find it extremely difficult to terminate their unhealthy relationship with drugs. This signifies that these young students are facing a serious problem that needs societal intervention. Hence, most universities in Nigeria establish guidance and counselling centres or units, and the counsellors are ready to assist students having problems. Most students dealing with drugs, however, do not seek the help of the university counsellors because they may not want people to know that they are abusing drugs, especially female drug abusers. In light of the above, the objectives of the study are to: find out the perception of female undergraduates on the most commonly abused drug among female university students in Kano State; understand the perception of female undergraduates on the prevalence of drug abuse among female university students in Kano State.

Methodology

Research Design, Population and Sample

The study used a survey design to find out the perceptions of female undergraduates about drug abuse among female university students in Kano State. The target population of this study comprised all the level 200 and 300 (female

undergraduates of Bayero University Kano, Yusuf Maitama Sule University Kano, and Kano University of Science and Technology Wudil from the department of education. According to the statistical report obtained from the Centre for Information Technology (CIT), the total number of female undergraduates in Bayero University Kano is one thousand two hundred and forty-two (1242), and according to the departmental record of students for the 2017/2018 session, the total number of female undergraduates in Yusuf Maitama Sule University is six hundred and seventy-one (671), while Kano University of Science and Technology female undergraduates are three hundred and ninety-three (393), making the total number of female students two thousand three hundred and six (2306).

Accordingly, the sample size of the study is 306 female undergraduates from Bayero University Kano, Yusuf Maitama Sule University Kano, and Kano University of Science and Technology Wudil. Out of the above sample, 164 female undergraduates at Bayero University, 89 female undergraduates at Yusuf Maitama Sule University Kano, and 53 female undergraduates at Kano University of Science and Technology Wudil were selected to form the sample size. The sample size was drawn from the total population using Research Advisors (2006). A proportionate sampling technique was used in selecting the sample for the study. Proportionate sampling is a sampling method used when the population is composed of several subgroups that are vastly different in number. The number of participants from each subgroup is determined by their number relative to the entire population. The total number of female undergraduates was two thousand three hundred and six (2306), and a simple random sampling technique was used to select three hundred and six (306) respondents. The table below provides a clearer view of the population and sample size of the study.

Table 1. Study Population and Sample Size

S/N	University	Programme	Level	Population	Sample Size
1.	BUK	B. A Ed	200	315	42
			300	320	42
		B. Sc Ed	200	297	39

			300	310	41
2.	KUST	B. Sc Ed	200	244	33
			300	149	20
3.	YUMSUK	B. A Ed	200	173	23
			300	129	17
		B. Sc Ed	200	242	32
			300	127	17
	Total			2306	306

Source: Fieldwork, 2020.

Data Collection Instrument

The instrument used in collecting data in this study is researcher-developed questionnaire titled Drug Abuse Inventory (DAI). The instrument consists of three sections A, B and C. Section “A” is concerned with personal data of the respondents such as university, year of study etc, section “B” consist of eleven (11) items related to drugs commonly abused by female university students and section “C” consists of four (4) items, prevalence of Drug Abuse among Female University Students. The instrument is based on four (4) likert scale.

Scoring of the Inventory

The Inventory was scored on (4) point Likert scale to find out the perception of female undergraduates on drugs of abuse and drug abuse. The response categories of the Inventory was weighted by assigned numerical value as: Strongly Agree= 4, Agree = 3, Disagree =2 and Strongly Disagree =1 while most of them= 3, many of them =2, some of them= 1 and none of them= 0. The sum of weight of all the items choose by the subject represents the individual’s total score.

Validity and Reliability of DAI

Validation of the instrument was obtained with the assistance of the Supervisor and other experts in the Department of Education Bayero University and Yusuf Maitama Sule University Kano. The useful suggestions such as modification of some items and grammatical errors were effected in drafting the final instrument with a view to eliminate ambiguities and irrelevant items to ensure a well-structured instrument.

The reliability of the instrument was obtained from pilot testing of the instrument using test retest method. Test retest type of reliability is determined by administering the same test twice to the same candidates under approximately the same conditions. The score obtained on the two occasions are then correlated to establish the degree to which two sets of scores correspond. A test that yields similar scores on two administrations where no significant event has taken place is highly reliable. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co- efficient was used in computing the correlation co-efficient of the instrument and a reliability index of 0.79 was obtained.

Data Collection and Analysis

The collection of data was done through personal administration and assistance from the research assistants who were trained on how to administer the instrument. The instrument was administered to level 2 and 3 students of Department of Education in the sampled schools and only female students participated in the research. Accordingly, Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20 was used in the analysis of the collected numerical data. The statistical tool that was used to analyze and interpret the data is descriptive. Descriptive statistical technique (mean and standard deviation) was used to answer research questions. T-test for independent sample and Analysis of variance (ANOVA) were used to test differences in all the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Below shows the summary of distribution of the respondents and answers to research questions

based on the data collected from the instruments of data collection employed in the process of data collection.

Table 2 shows the distribution of respondents based on university, level and programme. The distribution of respondents based on university shows that BUK has 164 respondents representing 53.6%, YUMSUK has 89 respondents representing 29.1% and KUST has 53 respondents representing 17.3%. The distribution of respondents based on programme shows that BUK has 84 B.A. ED students (51.2%) and 80 B.SC ED students

(48.8%), YUMSUK has 40 B.A. ED students (44.9%) and 49 B.SC ED students (55.1%), while, KUST has 53 B.SC ED students (100%). Hence, there are 124 B.A. ED students (40.5%) and 182 B.SC ED students (59.5%). Accordingly, the distribution of respondents based on level shows that there are 169 level 200 students (55.2%) and 137 level 300 students (44.8%).

Research Question One: What is the perception of female undergraduates on most commonly abused drug among female university students in Kano State?

Table 2. Distribution of Respondents Based on University, Level of Study and Programme

	University	Programme	Level	frequency	Percentage	
1	BUK	B.A ED	200	42	13.7	100%
			300	42	13.7	
		B. SC ED	200	39	12.7	
			300	41	13.3	
2	YUMSUK	B.A ED	200	23	7.52	
			300	17	5.56	
		B.SC ED	200	32	10.6	
			300	17	5.56	
3	KUST	B. SC	200	33	10.8	
			300	20	6.53	
Total				306	100	

Source: Fieldwork, 2020.

Table 3: Most Common Drug Abused by Female Undergraduate Students

Group	Mean	S. D.	Rank
Codeine	3.52	0.618	2
Marijuana	2.80	1.010	6
Rohypnol	3.37	0.787	3
Tramadol	2.94	1.024	5
Benylin	3.57	0.604	1
Tobacco	3.35	0.710	4
Heroine	2.80	1.022	6
Cocaine	1.85	0.846	10
Alcohol	2.04	0.905	9
Gadagi	2.64	1.071	7
Solution	2.56	0.947	8

Source: Fieldwork, 2020

Table 3 above shows that benylin has the highest mean score of 3.57, closely followed by codeine with a mean score of 3.52, rohypnol with a mean score of 3.37, tobacco with a mean score of 3.35, tramadol with a mean score of 2.94, heroin and

marijuana both with a mean score of 2.80, gadagi with a mean score of 2.64, solution with a mean score of 2.56, alcohol with a mean score of 2.04 and finally cocaine with a mean score of 1.85. Therefore, Benelyn is the most commonly

abused drug by female university students in Kano State with the highest mean score of (3.57).

Research Question Two: What is the perception of female undergraduates on the prevalence of drug abuse among female university students in Kano State.

Table 4 above shows the prevalence of Drug Abuse among Female University Students as perceived by female undergraduates in Kano

State. It shows that out of 164 female undergraduates from BUK, 146 (89%) perceived that female undergraduates abuse drugs. Out of 89 female undergraduates from YUMSUK, 54 (60.7%) perceived that female undergraduates abuse drugs and out of 53 female undergraduates from KUST, 28 (52.8%) perceived that Female Undergraduates abuse drugs. Therefore, out of the total number of 306 female Undergraduates in Kano State 228 (74.5%) perceived that Female Undergraduates in Kano State abuse drugs.

Table 4. Prevalence of Drug Abuse among Female University Students

S/N	University	Programme	Level	N	Prevalence
1	BUK	B.A ED	200	42	38(90.5%)
			300	42	36(85.7%)
		B. SC ED	200	39	35(89.7%)
			300	41	37(90.2%)
		Total		164	146 =89%
2	YUMSUK	B.A ED	200	23	15(65.2%)
			300	17	10(58.8%)
		B.SC ED	200	32	19(59.3%)
			300	17	10(58.8%)
		Total		89	54 =60.7%
3	KUST	B. SC ED	200	33	18(54.5%)
			300	20	10(50%)
		Total		53	28 =52.8%
		Total		306	228=74.5%

Source: Fieldwork, 2020

Table 5. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on Prevalence of Drug Abuse Among Female University Students Based on Universities

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	83.093	2	41.546	19.842	0.00
Within Groups	634.437	303	2.094		
Total	717.529	305			

Source: Fieldwork, 2020

Hypotheses Testing

Analysis of variance and t-test for independent sample was used for the analysis of the three hypotheses using statistical program for social sciences (SPSS) computer analysis.

HO1: There is no significant difference in the perception of female undergraduates on the prevalence of drug abuse among female university students in Kano State based on university.

Table 5 above shows Analysis of Variance of difference in the prevalence of drug abuse among female university students based on universities. The result shows the p-value of 0.00 tested at 0.05 with a 305 degree of freedom. The p-value (0.00) is less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant

difference in the perception of female undergraduates on the prevalence of drug abuse among female university students in Kano state is rejected. This means that there is significant difference in the perception of female undergraduates on the prevalence of drug abuse among female university students in Kano State.

Table 6. Post Hoc Test Analysis (Scheffe Test)

(I) Institutions of learning	(J) Institution	Mean difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
BUK	KUST	1.439	.229	.000
	YUMSUK	.301	.191	.288
KUST	BUK	-1.439	.229	.000
	YUMSUK	-1.138	.251	.000
YUMSUK	BUK	-.301	.191	.288
	KUST	1.138	.251	.000

Source: Fieldwork, 2020 (*The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level)

Table 7 t-test for Independent Sample Between Prevalence of Drug Abuse and Programme of Study

Programme	N	Mean	Df	Sd	t-value	P-value (2tailed)
B.A ED	124	7.94	304	1.820	2.175	0.30
B.SC ED	182	7.55		1.285		

Source: Fieldwork, 2020

Table 6 above present the post-hoc analysis (scheffe test) to show the direction of the difference in the perception of female undergraduates on drug abuse prevalence based on university. The table shows that there is significant difference between BUK and KUST (P-value=0.000) and KUST and YUMSUK (p-value=0.000) respectively, while the table present that there is no significant difference in the perception of female undergraduates on the prevalence of drug abuse among female university students between BUK and YUMSUK (p-value=0.288).

HO2: There is no significant difference in the perception of female undergraduates on the prevalence of drug abuse among female

university students in Kano State based on programme.

Table 7 above shows the test result of difference in prevalence of drug abuse among female university students based on program. The result shows the calculate t-value of 2.175 and p-00value of 0.30 tested at 0.05 with a 304 degree of freedom. The p-value (0.30) is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the perception of female undergraduates on the prevalence of drug abuse among female university students in Kano State based on programme is retained. This means that there is no significant difference in the perception of female undergraduates on the prevalence of drug abuse among female

university students in Kano State based on programme.

HO3: There is no significant difference in the perception of female undergraduates on the prevalence of drug abuse among female university students in Kano State based on level.

Table 8 above shows the test result of difference in prevalence of drug abuse among female university students based on level of study. The result shows the calculated t-value of 2.165 and p-value of 0.31 tested at 0.05 with a 305 degree

of freedom. The p-value (0.31) is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the perception of female undergraduates on the prevalence of drug abuse among female university students is retained. This means that, there is no significant difference in the perception of female undergraduates on the prevalence of drug abuse among female university students in Kano State based on level.

Table 8. t-test for Independent Sample of Prevalence of Drug Abuse Based on Level of Study

Level of Study	N	Mean	Sd	Df	t-cal	P-Value
Level 200	169	7.88	1.677	304	2.165	0.31
Level 300	137	7.50	1.312			

Source: Fieldwork, 2020

Discussion

This study was set up mainly to investigate the perceptions of female undergraduates about drug abuse among female university students in Kano State. In this study, drugs commonly abused as well as the prevalence of drug abuse in Kano State public universities were investigated using the Drug Abuse Inventory (DAI). The first research question reveals that Benylin (with a mean score of 3.57) is perceived as the most commonly abused drug among female university students in Kano State. The finding also reveals that cocaine (with a mean score of 1.85) is the least commonly abused drug among female university students in Kano State. The finding of Adeyemo, Ohaeri, Pat & Ogodo (2016) is not in conformity with the most commonly abused drug but is in conformity with the least abused drug. The study sought to determine the prevalence of drug abuse among students at the University of Benin. The study employs a descriptive survey design using a sample size of 800 students (44.6% female representation). The study found that alcohol and coffee were the most commonly abused drugs, while cocaine was the least. The finding is also not in agreement with the findings of Oshikoya & Alli

(2006) who conducted a survey with 807 out of 1000 respondents (80.7% response rate) on the perception of drug abuse among undergraduate students residing off-campus at Lagos State University. The study found that marijuana (45.7%) was the most commonly abused drug seen by most students. The study findings are also in disagreement with the findings of Adelekan, Abiodun, Obayan & Ogunremi (1998) who investigated the prevalence and pattern of substance use among undergraduate students at the University of Ilorin with 636 analysed questionnaires (out of which 41% were females). Contrary to this study's findings, Adelekan et al. (1998) provided the most commonly abused substances, which included salicylate analgesics.

This finding also contradicts the argument of Sharp & Rosen (2007) who maintained that females are more likely to participate in the use of recreational stimulants. Benylin is, however, a sedative that tranquillizes the central nervous system and induces a feeling of relaxation. However, a study conducted by Hali (2017) in Kano Metropolis found that the substance mainly abused by women was cough syrup or roche, while cocaine and steroids were the least abused. The study was conducted in Kano

Metropolis, where two of the three sampled universities are located. The finding of Hali (2017) is in agreement with this study's finding because Benelyn is also a cough syrup. Accordingly, Hali (2017) also found alcohol to be the least abused drug. The need to relieve stress or pressure emanating from role conflict may be the reason why benlyn is the most commonly abused drug by female undergraduate students. The drug will at least for a while allow users to forget about disappointments, probably because the reality of life has affected them more severely than expected and they have no other alternative to dealing with it (Matejovicova et al., 2015). Sedatives, among other drugs, are even relatively more accessible (Omotoso et al., 2021).

The second research question shows that the extent of drug abuse prevalence among female university students as perceived by female undergraduates in Kano State is high at 74.5%. It shows that out of 164 female undergraduates from BUK, 146 (89%) perceived that female undergraduates abuse drugs; out of 89 female students from YUMSUK 59 (66.2%) perceived that female undergraduates abuse drugs; and out of 53 female undergraduates from KUT, 28 (52.8%) perceived that female undergraduates abuse drugs. The study findings also corroborate the findings of Babalola, Akinlanmi & Ogunwale (2014) who examined the prevalence, pattern, and factors associated with psychoactive substance use among medical students at Olabisi Onabanjo University with a sample of 246 medical students (47.2% female representation) between September and October 2011. Babalola et al. (2014) found the lifetime prevalence of drug abuse among medical students in Olabisi Onabanjo at 65%.

The first hypothesis provides that there is a significant difference in the perception of female undergraduates about the prevalence of drug abuse among female university students based on the university. This finding also indicates that BUK has the highest prevalence of drug abuse among female university students with a mean score of 8.04, followed by YUMSUK with a mean score of 7.74 and finally KUST with 6.60 mean score. The findings from the analysis of hypothesis with a p-value of 0.00 (tested at a 0.05

level of significance) proved that there is a difference in the prevalence of drug abuse between the three sampled universities. This may be because, BUK is a federal institution, and the students may be more aware of the issue of drug abuse. This finding is in agreement with the finding of Onoja (2010) who compared the prevalence of drug abuse among students of private secondary schools and public secondary schools in Jos. A total of 250 self-administered questionnaires were distributed in each school using proportionate allocation by stratification. Onoja (2010) found that drug abuse was more prevalent in private schools than in government schools.

The second hypothesis maintains that there is no significant difference in the perception of female undergraduates about the prevalence of drug abuse among female university students in Kano State based on the programme. This finding also highlights that female students studying B.A. ED have the highest mean score of 7.94, compared to female students studying B.SC ED with a 7.55 mean score. The findings from the analysis of hypotheses with a p-value of 0.30 (tested at the 0.05 level of significance) proved that there is no significant difference in the prevalence of drug abuse between the programmes of study (B.A. ED and B.SC ED). This finding is in discordance with the findings of Bogowicz, Ferguson, Gilvarry, Kamali, Kaner & Newbury-Birch (2018) who examined the use of alcohol and drugs among medical and law students at a UK university using an anonymous cross-sectional questionnaire survey of first, second and final year medical and law students at a single UK university. With 1242 of 1577 respondents (78.8%), Bogowicz et al. (2018) found a difference in the prevalence of drug abuse (alcohol use disorders) between medical students and law students.

The third hypothesis purports that there is no significant difference in the perception of female undergraduates about drug abuse prevalence based on level. This finding also purports that level 200 female students have a mean score of 7.88 and level 300 female students have a mean score of 7.50. The findings from the analysis of hypotheses with a p-value of 0.31 (tested at a

0.05 level of significance) proved that there is no difference in the prevalence of drug abuse between levels 200 and 300. This finding is in conformity with the finding of Rebecca, Keith & Michelle (2015) studied correlates of over-the-counter drug use with students in health, physical activity, and leisure classes at one large public university using 339 respondents (more than half of whom are female respondents [59.2]). The study found no significant difference based on grade (level of study).

Conversely, this study's findings are in disagreement with the findings of Bewick, Moulhern & Stiles (2008). Bewick et al. (2008) describe the drinking patterns of UK full-time undergraduate students as they progress through their degree course. Data was collected for 3 years from 58995 undergraduate students who began their studies either in 2000 or 2001. Longitudinal data (i.e., years 1-3) were available for 225 students. The remaining 5670 students all responded to at least one of the three surveys (year 1, n = 2843; year 2, n = 2219; year 3, n = 1805). The study found that students' alcohol consumption declined over their undergraduate studies. This means that the prevalence of alcohol consumption is not the same across all levels of study. Thus, Bewick et al. (2008) discovered a difference in the prevalence of substance abuse among undergraduate students across levels of study. However, the findings of Babalola, Akinlanmi & Ogunwale (2014) also indicated a relationship between the prevalence of drug abuse among university students and the year of study. This finding also contradicts the finding of Schegute & Wasihun (2021), who reported a higher prevalence of khat use among 3rd and 4th year students.

Accordingly, drug abuse remains a problem affecting young adult female undergraduates in Nigeria. The findings of the study have implications for counselling by providing a hint on the most commonly abused drug and which students use drugs more. Such information can be utilised by university management, guidance, and counsellors, as well as the state in general. For example, the solution-focused brief therapy that concentrates on solutions to behavioural problems rather than the problems can utilise

these findings. Solutions to drug abuse by undergraduates can rally around such data to understand how the strengths and potentials of affected students can best be exploited.

Conclusion

Even with formal and informal strategies used by both the sampled institutions, family members, and the community at large, the problem of drug abuse continues to persist among female students. However, not much attention is given to counselling strategies. Female students can be immensely assisted by counsellors to overcome and manage their problems. In other words, the majority, if not all, of these female students with drug problems can be treated with counselling interventions. Since benylin is the most commonly abused drug by female university students, the university management should take the appropriate measures to ensure that benylin is not easily accessible within the university campus by preventing its sale. The university should also ensure that students found with benylin are punished accordingly (except strictly under a doctor's prescription). Based on the scope and limitations of the study, it is recommended that similar studies be carried out using distinct or different research techniques but on similar behaviour. The scope of the study was limited to undergraduate students from the faculty of education. Therefore, it is recommended that similar study should be conducted to cover students from other faculties of the university.

References

- Abdullahi, S.A. (2003). Youth deviance and traditional authority in Kano Metropolis. In Adamu, A. (Ed). *Chieftaincy and National Security: Some Issues*. Kano: Samarib.
- Adelekan, M.L, Abiodun, O.O, Obayan, A.O, Oni G., & Ogunremi, O.O. (1993). Psychological correlates of alcohol, tobacco and cannabis use: Findings from a Nigerian university. *Drug and Alcohol Dependence*, 33, 247-

256. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0376-8716\(93\)90111-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0376-8716(93)90111-3)

Adenugba, A.A. & Okeshola, F. B. (2018). Substance abuse among females in Nigeria, *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 9(5), 99-105. <https://doi.org/10.30845/ijbss.v9n5p12>

Adeyemo, F.O., Ohaeri B., Pat, U.O. & Ogodo, O. (2016) Prevalence of Drug Abuse Amongst University Students in Benin City, Nigeria. *Public Health Research*, 6(2), 31-37. <https://doi.org/10.5923/j.phr.20160602.01>

Asagba, R.B., Agberotimi, S.F. & Abayomi, O.O. (2021). Prevalence and psychological correlates of alcohol use among Nigerian university students. *Journal of Substance Use*, 26(6), 608-613. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14659891.2021.1875067>

Atwoli, L., Mungla, P.A., Ndungu, M.N., Kinoti, K.C. & Ogot, E.M. (2011). Prevalence of substance use among college students in Eldoret, Western Kenya. *BMC Psychiatry*, 11, 34 <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-244X-11-34>

Babalola, E.O, Akinlanmi, A. & Ogunwale, A. (2014). Who guards the guard: Drug use pattern among medical students in a Nigerian university. *Annals of Medical and Health Sciences Research*, 4(3), 397-403. <https://doi.org/10.4103/2141-9248.133467>

Bewick, B. M, Mulhern, B & Stiles, W.B (2008) Changes in undergraduate student alcohol consumption as they progress through university. *BMC Public Health*, 8, 163. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2458-8-163>

Bogowicz, P., Ferguson, J., Gilvarry, E., Kamali, F., Kanis, E. & Newbury-Birch, D. (2018). Alcohol and other substance use among medical and law students at a UK University: A cross sectional Questionnaire Survey. *Postgraduate medical journal*, 94(1109), 131-136. <https://doi.org/10.1136/postgradmedj-2017-135136>

Garba, A. (2003). *Youth and drug abuse in Nigeria: Strategies for counseling, management and control*. Kano: Matasa Press.

Haladu, A. A. (2003). Outreach strategies for curbing drug abuse among out-of-school youth in Nigeria: A Challenge for Community Based Organization (CBOS) in A Garba (ed) *Youth and drug abuse in Nigeria: Strategies for counseling management and control*. Kano: Matasa Press.

Hali, M. (2017). *The predisposing factors of substance abuse among women in Kano Metropolis*. (Unpublished M. Sc. Dissertation), Department of Sociology, Bayero University Kano.

Hindocha, C., Freeman, T.P., Ferris, J.A., Lynskey, M.T. & Winstock, A.R. (2016). No smoke without tobacco: A global overview of cannabis and tobacco routes of administration and their association with intention to quit. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 7(1), 104-110. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2016.00104>

Ibrahim, B., Bakori, F.I., Abdul-kadir, I.L. & Jabo, A.J. (2019). Influence of drug abuse on student's academic performance in selected senior secondary schools in Sokoto Local Government Sokoto State. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 3(12), 161-167.

Ibu, J. & Eni, E. (2018). Drug abuse prostitution tendency among female undergraduate students in three universities in South-South Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Advanced Studies*, 5(2), 43-47.

Igbo, E. (2007). *Introduction to criminology*. Nsukka: University of Nigeria Press Ltd.

Matejovicova, B., Trandzik, J., Schlarmanova, J., Boledovicova, M. & Veleminsky, M. (2015). Illegal drug use among female university students in Slovakia. *Medical Science Monitor*, 21, 254-261. <https://doi.org/10.12659/MSM.892068>

Muraguri, C. W. (2004). *The Role of Drama in Eradicating Drug Substance Abuse in Secondary Schools in Starehe and Kamukunji, Nairobi Province*. M. Ed. University of Nairobi, Nairobi.

Nalini, S., Joseph, L. & Sathya, K. (2016). Knowledge on drug abuse among nursing

students. *International Journal of Current Advanced Research*, 5(8), 1168-1179.

NDLEA. (1997). *Drug data collection and research*. Lagos: Drug Demand and Reduction Unit National Drug Law Enforcement Agency.

Okoro, R.N. & Lahai, U. (2021). Drug use among undergraduates in Maiduguri, Northeast Nigeria. *International Journal of Health Life Sciences*, 7(2), e113625.
<https://doi.org/10.5812/ijhls.113625>

Oliha, J.A. (2014). Adolescent and drug abuse in tertiary institution: Implication for counselling. *British Journal of Education*, 2(1), 1-9.

Omotoso, A.B., Mekanjuola, A.B. & Abiodun, O.A. (2021). Recreational use of psychoactive substances among secondary students in North Central Nigeria. *Journal of Substance Use*, 26(1), 73-78.
<https://doi.org/10.80/14659891.2020.1779361>

Onoja, M.O. (2010) *Prevalence of Substance Abuse among Secondary School Students*. A comparative Study of Government and Private Secondary Schools in Jos, Nigeria National Institute of Drug Abuse.

Oshikoya, K. & Alli, A. (2006). Perception of drug abuse amongst Nigerian undergraduates. *World Journal of Medical Sciences*, 1(2), 133-139.

Priyanka, S. & Ankita, T. (2016). A study of adolescent drug abuse in India. *America Journal of Research in Humanities, Arts and Social Sciences*, 15(2), 119-121.

Rebecca, A.V., Keith, A.K. & Michelle, L. (2015) Correlates to over-the-counter drug use among college students. *Journal of Substance Use*, 20(5), 310-314.
<https://doi.org/10.3109/14659891.2014.911978>

Shegute, T. & Wasihun, Y. (2021). Prevalence of substance use in university students, Ethiopia, Substance Abuse. *Research and Treatment*, 15, 1-16,
<https://doi.org/10.1177/11782218211003558>

Siro, A.A. (2014). Drug abuse and political thuggery among the youth in Kano Metropolis: A modern civilization or resource mismanagement? *Journal of Studies in Social Sciences*, 7(2), 144-163.

Yi, S., Peltzer, K., Pengpid, S. & Susilowati, I.H. (2017). Prevalence and associated factors of illicit drug use among university students in the association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN). *Substance Abuse Treatment, Prevention and Policy*, 12(9).
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s/3011-017-0096.3>

Appendix 1

¹ BUK represents Bayero University Kano

² KUST represents Kano University of Science and Technology

³ YUMSUK represents Yusuf Maitama Sule University Kano

⁴ DAI represents Drug Abuse Inventory